

BENEFITS

- Applicable to **opaque** and **vision units** of the buildings
- **Breathable** with high thermal insulation properties
- **Save, easy and fast on-site assembly**
- **Customisable** exterior finish
- Mainly made from **renewable biobased materials**
- Designed for **disassembly** for use in closed circular economy material loops

Project innovation fact sheet

Wood-based curtain wall façade system

APPLICATIONS

- Prefabricated building envelope
- Low-, mid- and high-rise buildings
- Opaque and vision units of the buildings

NEXT STEPS

- Increasing cost efficiency
- Increasing biobased parts
- Reducing weight
- Production process optimization

Wooden cladding

Biocomposite profile

Fireshield (plywood)

